

Studies on Some Thionaphthenophenazines.

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Condensation of some thionaphthaquinones with several *o*-phenylenediamines have been carried out and the properties of the thionaphthenophenazines studied. These condensations have been compared with those of isatins and coumaran-2 : 3-diones and the *o*-diamines.

IN continuation of our investigations on phenazines^{1,2}, we prepared a number of indophenazines³ of the type (I) by condensation of

yield, results of analysis and other details. All except two of the products, however, were cream to yellow in colour. Those two [sl. nos. 1 and 16(i)]

isatins with *o*-phenylenediamines. Replacement of isatins by coumaran-2 : 3 diones, however, did not give compounds of the type II; instead the furan ring opened up and gave IV which exist in the lactam form VIII stabilised by hydrogen bonding⁴.

It was, therefore considered interesting to condense a few thionaphthoquinones with some *o*-phenylenediamines to find out whether or not the hetero ring opens up in these condensations. It was, further thought, that if the thionaphthene ring remains intact, the phenazines obtained might be bright coloured substances capable of acting as dyes to wool, as is found to be the case with indophenazines³.

For the purpose of the present study, 4 : 5-dimethyl-, 4 : 5-dichloro-, 4 : 6-dibromo-, 4-methoxy-, 4-nitro-, 3-iodo-, 3-chloro-, 3-bromo- and 4-methyl-*o*-phenylenediamines were condensed with thionaphthoquinone and its 5-methyl- and 5-bromo- derivatives in hot acetic acid solution.

The condensation in some of these cases, may obviously lead to the production of structural isomers. It was, however, observed that in general, only one of the isomers is predominantly produced and this was isolated, purified and studied. In two cases however (sl nos. 15 and 16) the two isomers have been obtained in comparable amounts. Exact structural assignment was, however, not undertaken. The condensations occurred readily and the products were nicely crystalline, soluble in varying degrees in acetic acid, ethyl acetate, pyridine and nitrobenzene and are practically insoluble in ether, acetone and alcohol. The table gives the names,

were developed on wool but the shades were lighter than the parent compounds.

The elemental analysis of the thionaphthenophenazines agreed with the structure III. The substances are not soluble in alkali proving their non-acidic nature. Their IR spectra neither reveal the presence of -SH nor of -C=O, NH and amido groups as would have been expected if the thiophene ring had ruptured. It is thus concluded that thionaphthoquinones condensed in a manner analogous to isatins.

From the point of view of chemical behaviour aromaticity is found to increase from furan to pyrrole to thiophene. This gradation was previously explained on the basis of resonance energies and bond lengths. New and more accurate data, however, render the above explanation unsatisfactory and now the gradation is rationalised on the basis of electronegativity of the hetero atom and its polarisability⁵. Proceeding on the same lines it is understandable why ring opening occurs with coumarandiones and not with isatins and thionaphthenequinones.

Oxygen is more electronegative than both 'N' and 'S'. Similarly the polarisability also decreases in the order of O > N > S as is indicated by the ionisation potentials for water, ammonia and hydrogensulphide. During the condensation, therefore it is not surprising that the oxygen catches a proton, forms a covalent link to get converted to -OH with a simultaneous rupture of a carbon-oxygen bond where as with nitrogen and sulphur this does not happen. In support of this view may be cited the

TABLE

OP denotes *o*-phenylenediamine
TQ—denotes Thionaphthenequinone

TNP denotes Thionaphthophenazines

Sl. No.	Name of Azines	Reactants	(a) Appearance (b) Solvent	M.P. °C Yield % (Crude)	Formula	Analysis	
						Found	Reqd.
1.	2 : 3-Dimethyl-TNP	TQ + 4 : 5-dimethyl-OP	(a) Shining orange flakes (b) Nitrobenzene	336-37 50.0	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ S	C, 71.4 H, 4.9	C, 71.9 H, 4.5
2.	2 : 3 : 7-Trimethyl-TNP	5-Methyl-TQ + 4 : 5-dimethyl-OP	(a) Light yellow needles (b) Pyridine	197-98 46.3	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ S	N, 10.3	N, 10.1
3.	2 : 3-Dimethyl-7-bromo-TNP	5-Bromo-TQ + 4 : 5-dimethyl-OP	(a) Light yellow needles (b) Pyridine	232-33 80.2	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ BrS	C, 55.5 H, 3.4	C, 56.0 H, 3.2
4.	2 : 3-Dichloro-TNP	TQ + 4 : 5-dichloro-OP	(a) Light yellow shining flakes (b) Acetic acid	138-40 73.0	C ₁₄ H ₆ N ₂ SCl ₂	C, 54.8 H, 2.1	C, 55.1 H, 2.0
5.	2 : 3-Dichloro-7-methyl-TNP	5-Methyl-TQ + 4 : 5-dichloro-OP	(a) Brownish yellow Needles. (b) Pyridine	273-74 62.5	C ₁₅ H ₈ N ₂ Cl ₂ S	N, 8.9	N, 8.7
6.	2 : 3-Dichloro-7-bromo-TNP	5-Bromo-TQ + 4 : 5-dichloro-OP	(a) Light yellow needles (b) Nitrobenzene	289-90 —	C ₁₄ H ₅ N ₂ BrCl ₂	C, 43.4 H, 1.7	C, 43.8 H, 1.3
7.	2 : 4- or 1 : 3-Di-bromo-7-methyl-TNP.	5-Methyl-TQ + 4 : 6-dibromo-OP	(a) Light yellow needles (b) Toluene	266-67 74.0	C ₁₅ H ₈ Br ₂ N ₂ S	N, 7.0	N, 6.8
8.	2 : 4 : 7- or 1 : 3 : 7-Tribromo-TNP	5-Bromo-TQ + 4 : 6-dibromo-OP	(a) Light yellow needles (b) Chloroform & Toluene	296-97 74.5	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ Br ₃ N ₂ S	C, 35.4 H, 1.6	C, 35.7 H, 1.1
9.	2 or 3-Methoxy-TNP	TQ + 4-methoxy-OP	(a) Light yellow flakes (b) Ethanol	184-86 40.0	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₂ OS	C, 67.4 H, 4.1	C, 67.7 H, 3.8
10.	2 or 3-Methoxy-7-methyl-TNP	5-Methyl-TQ + 4-methoxy-OP	(a) Light yellow needles (b) Ethanol	207-08 26.0	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ OS	N, 10.4	N, 10.0
11.	2 or 3-Methoxy-7-bromo-TNP	5-Bromo-TQ + 4-methoxy-OP	(a) Yellow needles (b) Ethanol + Ethylacetate	185-86 45.5	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₂ OSBr	N, 8.5	N, 8.1
12.	2 or 3-Nitro-7-methyl-TNP	5-Methyl-TQ + 4-nitro-OP	(a) Intense yellow needles (b) Ethyl acetate	254-56 40.5	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂ S	C, 60.7 H, 3.5	C, 61.0 H, 3.1
13.	2- or 3-Nitro-7-bromo-TNP	5-Bromo-TQ + 4-nitro-OP	(a) Orange yellow needles (b) Pyridine	236-40 84.5	C ₁₄ H ₆ N ₃ SO ₂ Br	N, 9.7	N, 9.1
14.	1- or 4-Chloro-TNP	TQ + 3-chloro-OP	(a) Cream coloured needles (b) Acetone	179 56.5	C ₁₄ H ₇ N ₂ SCl	C, 62.5 H, 2.8	C, 62.1 H, 2.6
15.	1- or 4-Chloro-7-methyl-TNP	5-Methyl-TQ + 3-chloro-OP	(i)(a) Light yellow needles (b) Ethanol + Chloroform (ii)(a) Orange yellow (b) Pyridine	216-17 — 298-300 total 65.0	C ₁₅ H ₉ SN ₂ Cl -do-	(i)C, 63.0 H, 3.6 (ii)C, 62.7 H, 3.7	C, 63.3 H, 3.2 -do- -do-
16.	1- or 4-Chloro-7-bromo-TNP	5-Bromo-TQ + 3-chloro-OP	(i)(a) Shining intense buff coloured granules (b) Chloroform (ii)(a) Orange yellow (b) Pyridine	240-41 326-27 total 65.0	C ₁₄ H ₆ N ₂ BrClS -do-	(i)N, 8.9 (ii)N, 9.0	N, 8.8 -do-
17.	1- or 4-Iodo-TNP	TQ + 3-iodo-OP	(a) Light yellow flakes (b) Ethyl acetate	170 84.0	C ₁₄ H ₇ N ₂ SI	C, 46.8 H, 2.2	C, 46.4 H, 1.9
18.	1- or 4-Iodo-7-methyl-TNP	5-Methyl-TQ + 3-iodo-OP	(a) Dirty white needles (b) Methyl alcohol	185-86 53.5	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₂ SI	N, 7.5	N, 7.4
19.	1- or 4-Iodo-7-bromo-TNP	5-Bromo-TQ + 3-iodo-OP	(a) Cream coloured flakes (b) Ethyl acetate + Acetic acid	225-26 45.3	C ₁₄ H ₆ N ₂ SBrI	N, 6.5	N, 6.3
20.	1- or 4-Bromo-TNP	TQ + 3-bromo-OP	(a) Dirty light yellow needles (b) Ethyl acetate	154 48.0	C ₁₄ H ₇ N ₂ SBr	C, 53.3 H, 2.5	C, 53.3 H, 2.2
21.	2 : 7- or 3 : 7-Di-methyl-TNP	5-Methyl-TQ + 4-methyl-OP	(a) Cream coloured needles (b) Ethyl acetate + Methyl alcohol	183-84 52.0	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ S	C, 72.4 H, 4.9	C, 72.7 H, 4.5

fact that dil. acids can smoothly decompose substituted furans to a 1:4-diketone, while pyrroles give recognisable salts which then polymerise, and thiophenes remain unaffected.

Another factor may be operating. Opening of the hetero rings of the quinones during condensation would mean the generation of structures IV, V and VI, which may be stabilised as VII, VIII and IX. The nature of the condensation products may hence be governed by the relative stability of structures I, II and III and of VII, VIII, and IX. Obviously structure VIII is more stable than II while I and III are stabler than VII and IX respectively.

Experimental

Preparation of Thionaphthophenazines :

The following general procedure was adopted :
To a hot solution of the thionaphthoquinone in glacial

acetic acid was added a solution of the diamine in warm acetic acid and the mixture refluxed for some minutes to ensure complete reaction.

The precipitated product was removed by filtration and crystallised from suitable solvents several times to get pure product.

References

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